

4-Quinazolones—II Synthesis of Some Imidazo [1,5-a] Quinazolones

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The synthesis of 4-phenylimidazo [1,5-a] quinazolin-5 (4H)-one (IIIa) and its 1-substituted analogues (IIIb-f) is described.

The imidazo [1,5-a] quinazolones (III) represent a heterocyclic system with nitrogen bridgehead which has not been hitherto reported in the literature. We now report the synthesis of 4-phenylimidazo [1, 5-a] quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IIIa) and its 1-substituted analogues (IIIb-f).

Our approach to this synthesis is an adaptation of the procedure for the preparation of 2-azaindolizines¹ and therefore, our first choice of an intermediate which might be cyclised into 1-methyl-4-phenylimidazo [1,5-a] quinazolin-5 (4H)-one (IIIb), was 2-acetamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIb). This has been realised since reductive acetylation of 2-oximinomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one² with zinc dust and a mixture of acetic acid and acetic anhydride readily afforded IIb which, on cyclodehydration with polyphosphoric acid, furnished the desired imidazoquinazolone (IIIb).

This initial success led us to concentrate our efforts on the most suitable starting material, 2-aminomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I), since it could be converted into its N-carboxamido derivatives for subsequent cyclisation into other imidazoquinazolones. For this purpose, I was obtained from 2-bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one² by Gabriel synthesis. Interaction with potassium phthalimide in dimethylformamide gave 2-phthalimidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one, which on hydrolysis with hydrazine hydrate afforded I. Warming with acetic anhydride gave the acetamido compound IIb, identical with the specimen obtained as above by a different route. 2-Benzamidomethyl (IIc), 2-*p*-chlorobenzamidomethyl-(IId), 2- α -naphthamidomethyl — (IIe), and 2-phenylacetamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIf) were prepared from I by Schotten-Baumann method with appropriate acid chlorides, while 2-formamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIa) was obtained by treatment with a warm mixture of formic acid and acetic anhydride. Cyclodehydration of the amides IIa-f with polyphosphoric acid afforded 4-phenylimidazo [1,5-a] quinazolin-5 (4H)-one (IIIa) and its 1-methyl- (IIIb), 1-phenyl-(IIIc), 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-(IIId), 1- α -naphthyl- (IIIe), and 1-benzyl- (IIIf) analogues respectively. The scheme adopted for the synthesis and a plausi-

1. K. Winterfield and H. Franzke, *Angew. Chem. Intern. Ed. Engl.*, 1963, 2, 736.
2. Part I: B. D. Singh and D. N. Chaudhury, *This Journal*, 1968, 45, 311.

ble mechanism for the cyclodehydration are given below :

IIa, IIIa. R = H

IIb, IIIb. R = CH₃

IIc, IIIc. R = C₆H₅

IId, IIId. R = *p*-ClC₆H₄

IIe, IIIe. R = α -C₁₀H₇

IIf, IIIf. R = C₆H₅CH₂

The initial step is the intramolecular nucleophilic attack of the ring nitrogen atom on the carbonyl carbon of the side chain amido group. This is followed by the acid-catalysed dehydration and the protonated cation thus formed ejects a proton leading to the formation of the imidazoquinazolones IIa-f.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps are uncorrected. Organic extracts were dried with Na₂SO₄. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°. PPA used was of BDH laboratory Reagent grade.

2-Bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one. The reported procedure² was modified as follows for purer product and better yield. After refluxing a mixture of 2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (2.36 g.), freshly prepared NBS (1.78 g) and benzoyl peroxide (0.02 g) in CCl₄ (10 ml) close to an illuminated 60-watt lamp for 4 hr, the solvent was completely distilled off under reduced pressure. The dry solid residue was powdered, washed thoroughly with water to remove succinimide and then with Me₂CO to dissolve away the unreacted quinazolone. Crystallisation from benzene gave the *bromo compound* as off-white prisms (2.5 g; 80%), m.p. 187-188° (lit², m.p. 181° with previous sintering at 179°).

2-Phthalimidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one. To a solution of the above compound (11 g) in warm DMF was added powdered K-phthalimide (7.3 g) and the mixture heated on water bath for 1 hr with occasional shaking. It was cooled, diluted with CHCl₃ (50 ml) and poured into water (250 ml). The CHCl₃ layer was separated, the aq. phase

extracted with CHCl_3 (20 ml \times 2) and the combined CHCl_3 extract washed with 0.1N NaOH (40 ml), water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent to the point of incipient crystallisation followed by the addition of light petroleum (60 ml) induced rapid crystallisation. The crystals were filtered, washed with light petroleum and recrystallised from benzene to yield the *phthalimido ester* as colorless needles (12 g; 90%), m.p. 250°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 4.1; N, 11.2. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ requires C, 72.4; H, 3.9; N, 11.0%).

2-Aminomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I). A mixture of the preceding ester (3.8 g), 80% hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) and MeOH (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 hr. After cooling, water (12 ml) was added and MeOH distilled off under reduced pressure. Conc. HCl (10 ml) was added to the residual aq. suspension and the mixture heated under reflux for 1.5 hr. On cooling to 0°, crystalline phthalhydrazide that separated was filtered off, the filtrate and washings (with conc. HCl) were combined and neutralised with 15N NH_4OH when a colorless precipitate was obtained. After keeping it in the refrigerator overnight, the solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from MeOH to yield I as colorless needles (1.3 g; 52%), m.p. 164-165°. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 5.4; N, 16.6. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires C, 71.7; H, 5.1; N, 16.7%). Its *hydrochloride* melted at 250°. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 4.7; N, 14.8. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{OCl}$ requires C, 62.6; H, 4.8; N, 14.6%).

2-Formamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIa) To a solution of I (1 g) in 99% formic acid (15 ml) at 60°, Ac_2O (7 ml) was added dropwise with occasional external cooling to maintain the temperature. After the addition, the reaction solution was allowed to attain room temperature at which it was kept for 0.5 hr and then poured into ice water, neutralised with 15N NH_4OH when a precipitate was obtained. It was chilled in an ice bath, the solid was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum gave pure IIa as colorless needles (1 g; 90%), m.p. 184-185°. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 4.8; N, 14.8. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ requires C, 68.8; H, 4.6; N, 15.0%).

2-Acetamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIb). (a) An intimate mixture of 2-oximinomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one² (2 g) and Zn dust (10 g) was added slowly during 1 hr to a stirred mixture of AcOH (50 ml) and Ac_2O (50 ml), maintained at 20-30°. The mixture was maintained at this temperature by cooling during addition and 1 hr after addition. The solution was filtered, excess solvent distilled off when a highly crystalline precipitate separated out on standing. It was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and alcohol to afford IIb as colorless needles (1.4 g; 63%), m.p. 234-235°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 5.3; N, 14.1. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ requires C, 69.6; H, 5.1; N, 14.3%). It readily dissolves in alcohol and is almost insoluble in ethyl acetate.

(b) I (1 g), on warming with Ac_2O (5 ml) afforded IIb which was purified as in (a). Yield (1 g; 86%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 234-235°.

2-Benzamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIc). Benzoyl chloride (2 ml) was added to a suspension of I (1 g) in 4N aq. NaOH (30 ml) and the mixture shaken vigorously during 10-15 min. The solid which separated was filtered off, washed repeatedly with cold water, and crystallised from methanol to give IIc as colorless needles (1 g; 70%), m.p. 209° with previous sintering at 207°. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 5.0; N, 11.6. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ requires C, 74.3; H, 4.7; N, 11.8%).

2-*p*-Chlorobenzamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (II_d). It was prepared from I (1 g) and *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride (2 ml) according to the method described for the preparation of II_c. Crystallisation from alcohol gave colorless felted needles (0.9 g; 58%), m.p. 250-251°. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 4.3; N, 10.5. C₂₂H₁₆N₃O₂Cl requires C, 67.8; H, 4.1; N, 10.7%).

2-Naphthamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (II_e). It was obtained from I (1 g) and α -naphthoyl chloride (2 ml) as above. It was crystallised from alcohol to give colorless needles (1 g; 65%), m.p. 253-254°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 4.4; N, 10.2. C₂₆H₁₉N₃O₂ requires C, 77.0; H, 4.7; N, 10.3%).

2-Phenylacetamidomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (II_f). To a suspension of I (1 g) in satd. aq. NaHCO₃ (50 ml), phenylacetyl chloride (2 ml) was added and the mixture vigorously shaken for 20 min. The solid which separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol to give II_f as colorless needles (1 g; 62%), m.p. 178-179°. (Found: C, 74.6; H, 5.4; N, 11.1. C₂₃H₁₉N₃O₂ requires C, 74.8; H, 5.1; N, 11.3%).

General procedure for the preparation of imidazoquinazolones (III_{a-f}) by cyclisation of the amides (II_{a-f}) with PPA.

The amide (1 g) in PPA (20 g) was heated with occasional stirring in an oil bath at the stated temperature (internal) for a specified period (see below). The solution was poured into ice water stirred and neutralised with 15N NH₄OH when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate furnished the pure imidazoquinazolone.

At 130-135° for 1.5 hr, II_a gave 4-phenylimidazo [1,5-a] quinazolin-5(4H)-one (III_a) as light yellow needles (0.8 g; 85%), m.p. 193°. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 4.4; N, 16.3. C₁₆H₁₁N₃O requires C, 73.5; H, 4.2; N, 16.0%).

At 130-135° for 1.5 hr, II_b gave 1-methyl-4-phenylimidazo-[1,5-a] quinazolin-5(4H)-one (III_b) as yellow needles (0.75 g; 80%), m.p. 193°. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 4.9; N, 15.1. C₁₇H₁₃N₃O requires C, 74.1; H, 4.7; N, 15.2%).

At 130-135° for 1.5 hr, II_c gave 1,4-diphenylimidazo [1,5-a] quinazolin-5(4H)-one (III_c) as colorless needles (0.7 g; 73%), m.p. 260-261°. (Found: C, 78.0; H, 4.6; N, 12.2. C₂₂H₁₅N₃O requires C, 78.3; H, 4.4; N, 12.4%).

At 185-190° for 2 hr, II_d gave 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-phenylimidazo [1,5-a] quinazolin-5(4H)-one (III_d) as colorless needles (0.8 g; 84%), m.p. 248-249°. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 4.0; N, 11.1. C₂₂H₁₄N₃OCl requires C, 71.0; H, 3.7; N, 11.3%).

At 100-110° for 1 hr, II_e gave 1- α -naphthyl-4-phenylimidazo-[1,5-a] quinazolin-5

(4H)-one (IIIe) as light yellow needles (0.7 g ; 73%), m.p. 179°. (Found: C, 80.4 ; H, 4.1 ; N, 10.6. $C_{26}H_{17}N_3O$ requires C, 80.6 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 10.8%).

At 130-135° for 1 hr, II f gave 1-benzyl-4-phenylimidazo-[1,5-a] quinazolin-5(4H)-one (III f) as off-white needles (0.75 g ; 79%), m.p. 165°. (Found C, 78.8 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 12.2. $C_{23}H_{17}N_3O$ requires C, 78.6 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 11.9%).

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